

A Study On The Preference And Satisfaction Of The Rural People Towards E-Commerce In Melagaram, Tenkasi District.

Deepa Lakshmy. R

Reg No: 20221241012003

Ph. D Part Time Research Scholar Department of Commerce and Research

Sarah Tucker College, Perumalpuram. Tirunelveli-7

Email: dlakshmy@yahoo.com

Abstract:

The main aim of the study is to find about the satisfaction of rural people in Melagaram with pre-purchase decision, purchase decision and post purchase decision towards e-commerce and know the preference of rural people to buy products on e-commerce. The population of the study constitutes all the customers of e-commerce in rural areas of Melagaram in Tenkasi district. The sample size is fixed as 120. Convenient sampling method is used for selecting customers of E-commerce. Both primary and secondary data are collected. Primary data are collected from E-commerce customers in the rural areas of Melagaram in Tenkasi district and secondary data are collected from books, journals and internet. Structured questionnaire is used to collect primary data. It is concluded that the rural people are satisfied with E-commerce. Convenience is an important factor that drives the rural people towards E-commerce and rural people are using E-commerce to purchase different types of products. The result of the study reveals that most of the customers prefer to buy goods online based on user reviews, easy EMI options, availability of sufficient information about the product, facility for returning the product and facility for order-tracking details.

Key Words: Satisfaction, Pre-purchase decision, Purchase decision and Post purchase decision.

Introduction:

E-commerce is very newer and popular means of doing business. E-commerce is a boom in the modern business. It simply means the activity of buying and selling of products on online services or over the internet. E-commerce is a paradigm shift influencing both the sellers and the customers. E-commerce is witnessing a tremendous growth around the globe. The popularity of e-commerce, e-payment, e-servicing, etc. has been increased hugely by the internet and smart phones diffusion. There are a large number of e-commerce websites such as Amazon, Myntra and Flipkart which offers a vast variety of products to the customers.

Significance Of The Study:

As the e-commerce and its auxiliary activities are a newer phenomenon and ever growing one, only few studies have been done in this milieu, especially in the rural context. Hence there is a wide scope for the studies on the customer's perception and attitude towards the virtual shopping and e-services. There is an increasing trend in the popularity and exertion among virtual community to exploit the resources through internet. In the earlier stage of e-commerce pursuit, the

services and facilities were confined only to the urban people as they were affordable to own a smart phone and better connectivity. But now, it has widened to semi urban areas as well as rural areas.

Objectives Of The Study:

- 1) To study about the satisfaction of rural people in Melagaram with pre-purchase decision, purchase decision and post purchase decision towards E-commerce.
- 2) To know the preference of rural people in Melagaram to buy products on e-commerce.

Methodology:

The population of the study constitutes all the customers of E-commerce in rural areas of Melagaram in Tenkasi district. The sample size is fixed as 120. Convenient sampling method is used for selecting customers of e-commerce. Both primary and secondary data are collected. Primary data are collected from e-commerce costumers in the rural areas of Melagaram in Tenkasi district and secondary data are collected from books, journals and internet. Structured questionnaire is used to collect primary data.

Analysis And Interpretation:

Table 1
Ranking of Preference to buy products on internet

Sl. No	Products	Average	Rank
1.	Books	60.76	I
2.	Airlines reservation/Railway ticket booking	49.83	VI
3.	Electronic goods	58.70	II
4.	Share trading	47.44	VII
5.	Online magazines & Journals	46.01	IX
6.	Apparels	51.72	III
7.	Gifts, Greetings, Flowers	50.40	V
8.	Banking	51.67	IV
9.	Music	44.25	X
10.	Others	47.37	VIII

Source: Primary data

It is seen from the result obtained through Garret Ranking for the preference to buy products on internet. Books rank first with a mean score of (60.76), electronic goods rank second with a mean score of (58.70), apparels rank third with a mean score of (51.72), banking ranks fourth with a mean score of (51.67), gifts, greetings, flowers rank fifth with a mean score of (50.40), airlines reservation/railway ticket booking ranks sixth with a mean score of (49.83), share trading ranks seventh with a mean score of (47.44) and music ranks last rank with a mean score of (44.25). **Association between demographic profile of rural people and satisfaction with pre-**

purchase decision towards e-commerce

In order to find out the association between the demographic profile of rural people and satisfaction with pre-purchase decision towards E-commerce, 'ANOVA' test is used. The following hypothesis is framed. **The null hypothesis (H₀)- "There is no significant association between Satisfaction with Pre-Purchase Decision towards e-commerce and demographic profile of rural people in Tenkasi District"**. The result of 't' test for association between satisfaction with pre-purchase decision towards e-commerce and demographic profile of rural people is presented in Table 2.

Table 2
Association between Demographic Profile of Rural people and Satisfaction with Pre-Purchase Decision towards E-commerce

Satisfaction with Pre-Purchase Decision towards E-commerce	Demographic Profile of Rural people [F Statistics]						
	Age	Gen der	Mar ital Stat	Nu mbe r of	Qua lific atio n	Occ upat ion	Hou seho ld
Convenience	1.416	4.127*	6.480*	2.690*	8.106*	7.885*	6.247*
Price of the product	3.378*	5.141*	6.099*	7.556*	8.270*	8.495*	5.518*
Quality of the product	6.405*	8.658*	7.603*	0.923	6.819*	8.642*	1.968
Variety	2.196	9.006*	5.145*	9.977*	4.796*	8.929*	5.242*
User friendly websites	7.914*	8.903*	8.907*	8.855*	9.666*	5.442*	3.674*
Attractive discounts	7.088*	1.221	7.777*	6.625*	5.292*	9.865*	7.998*
User rating and testimonials	7.874*	9.011*	2.227	7.401*	8.150*	3.243*	1.332
Availability of the required product	9.206*	1.451	1.225	2.866*	5.843*	5.795*	4.992*

Source: Computed Data

It is understood from table 2 that there is a significant relationship between demographic profile variables of rural people namely gender, marital status, number of members in the family, qualification, occupation and

household monthly income and satisfaction with the pre-purchase decision towards e-commerce in terms of convenience, price of the product, quality of the product, variety, user friendly websites, attractive discounts,

user rating and testimonials and availability of the required product. **Association between demographic profile of rural people and satisfaction with Purchase decision towards e-commerce.** In order to find out the association between the demographic profile of rural people and satisfaction with purchase decision towards e-commerce, 'ANOVA' test is used. The following hypothesis is framed. **The null**

hypothesis (H₀)- "There is no significant association between Satisfaction with Purchase Decision towards E-commerce and demographic profile of rural people in Melagaram, Tenkasi District". The result of 't' test for association between satisfaction with purchase decision towards e-commerce and demographic profile of rural people is presented in Table 3

Table 3
Association between Demographic Profile of Rural people and Satisfaction with Purchase Decision towards E-commerce

Satisfaction with Purchase Decision towards e-commerce	Demographic Profile of Rural people [F Statistics]						
	Age	Gen der	Mari tal Stat	Num ber of	Qual ifica tion	Occ upat ion	Hou seho ld
Delivery period	9.720*	6.340*	5.547*	7.421*	5.482*	5.951*	7.559*
Security of payment	4.852*	0.796	4.413*	6.809*	5.212*	2.751*	7.348*
Privacy of personal information	5.013*	6.292*	5.848*	5.380*	5.030*	3.305*	7.390*
Home delivery charges	4.355*	7.162*	5.795*	1.269	6.051*	6.514*	3.093*

Source: Computed Data

It is understood from table 3 that there is a significant relationship between demographic profile variables of rural people namely age, gender, marital status, number of members in the family, qualification, occupation and household monthly income and satisfaction with purchase decision towards e-commerce in terms of delivery period, security of the payment, privacy of personal information and home delivery charges. **Association between Demographic profile of rural people and satisfaction with post-purchase decision towards E-commerce** In order to find out the association between the demographic profile of rural people and

satisfaction with post purchase decision towards E-commerce, 'ANOVA' test is used. The following hypothesis is framed. **The null hypothesis (H₀)- "There is no significant association between Satisfaction with Post Purchase Decision towards e-commerce and demographic profile of rural people in Melagaram, Tenkasi District"**. The result of 't' test for association between satisfaction with post purchase decision towards online purchase and demographic profile of rural people is presented in Table 4.

Table 4
Association between Demographic Profile of Rural people and Satisfaction with Post Purchase Decision towards E-commerce

Satisfaction with Post Purchase Decision towards e-commerce	Demographic Profile of Rural people [F Statistics]						
	Age	Gen der	Mari tal Stat us	Num ber of	Qual ifica tion	Occ upat ion	Hou seho ld Mon
Satisfaction of the quality of the product	7.702*	7.646*	6.978*	6.500*	8.198*	4.182*	6.377*
Assurance of after sales services	3.572*	1.924	1.206	9.998*	4.356*	6.452*	10.352*
Safe delivery of the product	4.389*	2.015*	6.530*	10.416*	9.489*	1.258	7.441*
Easy to return products	6.280*	0.224	6.528*	7.754*	8.816*	8.130*	7.050*

Source: Computed Data

It is understood from table 4 that there is a significant relationship between demographic profile variables of rural people namely age, gender, marital status, number of members in the family, qualification, occupation and household monthly income and satisfaction with post purchase decision towards e-commerce in terms of satisfaction of the quality of the product, assurance of after sales service, safe delivery of the product and easy to return products.

Group of rural people and Level of satisfaction on purchase decision on E-commerce

Male and female have different level of satisfaction on purchase decision on E-commerce namely satisfaction with the pre-purchase decision on E-commerce, satisfaction with the purchase decision on E-commerce, satisfaction with the post-purchase decisions on E-commerce and overall satisfaction towards purchase decision on E-commerce. While male rural people have satisfaction towards different

dimensions of purchase decision on E-commerce at a high level and female rural people have satisfaction towards different dimensions of purchase decision on E-commerce at a lower level. Hence an attempt has been made to find out whether there is a significant difference among male and female rural people with reference to the level of satisfaction on purchase decision on E-commerce. The following hypotheses were framed for finding out the significant difference among male and female rural people with respect to the level of satisfaction on purchase decision on E-commerce. **Null Hypothesis (H₀):** There is no significant difference among gender group of rural people with respect to the level of satisfaction on purchase decision on E-commerce. The following table shows the result of the 't' test for significant difference among the gender group of rural people with respect to the level of satisfaction on purchase decision on E-commerce.

Table 5
ANOVA for Significant difference among Gender Group of rural people with respect to the level of satisfaction on purchase decision on E-commerce

Level of satisfaction on purchase decisions on E-commerce	Gender Group		t Value	p Value
	Male	Female		
Satisfaction with pre-purchase decisions on E-commerce	48.21 (2.76)	48.61 (3.42)	1.772	0.077
Satisfaction with purchase decisions on E-commerce	19.32 (2.49)	19.98 (1.90)	3.951	0.000
Satisfaction with the post-purchase decisions on E-commerce	18.99 (2.06)	19.44 (2.20)	2.973	0.003
Overall satisfaction of purchase decisions on E-commerce	127.37 (6.48)	129.07 (6.57)	3.522	0.000

Source: Computed Data

Note: 1. The value within bracket refers to SD

Since the 'p' value is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis is rejected and the alternative hypothesis is accepted at 5% level of significance with regard to level of satisfaction on purchase decisions on E-commerce namely satisfaction with on purchase decisions, satisfaction with post-

purchase decisions and overall satisfaction towards E-commerce. Hence there is a significant difference among the gender group of rural people with regard to level of satisfaction on purchase decisions on E-commerce namely satisfaction with on purchase decisions, satisfaction with the post-purchase decisions and overall satisfaction towards E-commerce. Based on

Duncan Multiple Range Test (DMRT) the female rural people significantly differ with the male rural people on satisfaction with on purchase decision, satisfaction with post-purchase decisions and overall satisfaction towards E-commerce. Since the 'p' value is greater than 0.05, the null hypothesis is accepted and the alternative hypothesis is rejected at 5% level of significance with regard to level of satisfaction on purchase decision one-commerce namely satisfaction with the pre-purchase decision on E-commerce. Hence there is no significant difference among the gender group with respect to level of satisfaction on purchase decisions on E-commerce namely satisfaction with the pre-purchase decisions on e-commerce. It is concluded that no significant difference among gender group of rural people with respect to level of satisfaction on purchase decisions on E-commerce namely satisfaction with the pre-purchase decisions on E-commerce.

Suggestions:

Most of the rural people agree that provision of combo offers by the sellers induce them to prefer e-shopping. Thus, it is suggested that to attract more rural people online traders may give combo offers frequently, which helps traders not only to attract new consumer but also retain the existing ones, and consumer are happy to buy more goods at a low price.

Rural people should be educated on e-commerce procedures with proper steps to be following while involved in e-commerce.

Conclusion:

It is concluded that the rural people in Melagaram are satisfied with E-commerce. Convenience is an important factor that drives the rural people towards E-commerce and rural people are using E-commerce to purchase different types of products. The result of the study reveals that most of the customers prefer to buy goods online based on user reviews, easy EMI options, availability of sufficient information about the product, facility for returning the product and facility for order-tracking details. Hence, E-retailers have to constantly ascertain their customers' expectations, initiate necessary steps at the earliest to contain problems faced by them, offer full-fledged services like the sale of quality goods at a cheap price, replacement of damaged goods and expeditious delivery. Such services will offer

easy customer satisfaction, help sellers retain the existing customers and attract new ones.

References

- 1) Farooq Ahmed (2001). Electronic Commerce: An Indian Perspective: International Journal of Law and Information Technology; Vol.9, No.2, 2001, pp.133 - 170.
- 2) Shweta Sharma, Sugandha Mittal (2010). Prospects of E-commerce in India. Management Department Swami Devi Dayal, Institute of Engineering and Technology Barwala Haryana, India.
- 3) Bhaskar, B. (2003). Electronic Commerce: Framework Technologies and applications. New Delhi, Tata Mc Graw Hill, 2003.
- 4) Murthy, C.S.V. (2011). E-commerce: Concept, Models and Strategies. Himalaya Publishing House, Mumbai.